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INTEGRATING POETIC TEXTS INTO GRAMMAR INSTRUCTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION WITH EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE¹

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Abstract. This study explores the effectiveness of integrating poetic texts into grammar instruction in higher education. The research aims to enhance students' grammatical competence through a methodology that combines linguistic, aesthetic, and communicative dimensions of language learning. A pedagogical experiment was conducted involving 179 students, divided into experimental and control groups. While the experimental group was taught using poetic texts as a central instructional tool, the control group followed traditional grammar teaching methods. The study employed a mixed-method approach, including diagnostic and control testing, observation, and mathematical-statistical analysis. The results demonstrated that students in the experimental group showed significantly higher improvement in grammatical competence compared to those in the control group. The findings indicate that poetic texts facilitate deeper understanding of grammatical structures by presenting them in meaningful, contextualized, and emotionally engaging forms. The research confirms that the integration of literary materials into grammar instruction not only strengthens students' theoretical knowledge but also improves their ability to apply grammatical rules in real communicative situations. The study suggests that incorporating poetic texts into language curricula can serve as an effective pedagogical strategy in higher education.

Keywords: grammatical competence, poetic texts, grammar instruction, higher education, experimental study, language teaching, SMILE method.

Introduction. In modern higher education, mastering a foreign language, particularly German grammar, is not only a matter of theoretical knowledge but also a practical skill essential for effective communication. From this point of view, the development of new pedagogical approaches to effectively improve grammatical competence

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has become one of the most pressing issues in the educational process today (Ellis, 2006; Hymes, 1972). In this regard, the methodology of teaching grammar based on poetic texts, with its didactic, linguopoetic, and cultural-aesthetic potential, can serve as an important basis for modern integrative educational models.

The issue of improving grammatical competence in foreign language education is considered one of the most relevant and constantly researched areas of pedagogy today. A deep understanding of the grammatical system of a language is essential for effective and coherent communication. In this process, the application of poetic texts to the educational process makes the mastery of grammatical units more effective and meaningful (Collie & Slater, 1987; Belke, 2009).

The rhythmic structure, syntactic conciseness and figurative expressive means of poetic works encourage students to perceive grammatical phenomena not only as dry rules, but also as living linguistic phenomena (Dhoni, 2012). Thus, the topic of the dissertation reveals the linguodidactic significance of the methodology aimed at improving grammatical competence on the basis of poetic texts, and also offers an effective approach that can be used in higher education practice.

The deductive (formal-prescriptive) approach used in traditional grammar training is based on the principle of first stating grammatical phenomena as rules and then reinforcing them through exercises. Although this model allows for a logical and consistent mastery of the language system, it may not sustainably stimulate students' cognitive activity and learning motivation if it is not sufficiently integrated with the communicative context. In particular, the complexity of the morphological and syntactic system of the German language (inflectional forms, article and conjugation system, positional features of the verb) makes it difficult to master grammatical units based only on rules and transformational exercises.

In the process of studying the language system on a scientific basis, various approaches to the concept of grammar have been formed. F. de Saussure interpreted language as a system with an internal structure and identified syntagmatic (sequential connections) and paradigmatic (choice between options) relations as the main principles of

grammar. This approach made it possible to explain grammatical units through their place and function within the system (Saussure, 1916).

L. Bloomfield, within the framework of structuralist linguistics, analyzed grammar as a system of rules and regulations based on form. He believed that language units are formed on the basis of phonological and morphological units that have a strict order; grammatical construction determines the order of their combination. This approach separated grammar from content and emphasized the centrality of structure (Bloomfield, 1933).

N. Chomsky interprets grammar as a system of internal grammatical knowledge formed in the human mind, that is, language competence. He explains language at two levels: language competence (competence) - mental grammatical mechanisms of a person; speech practice (performance) - use in speech. According to the generative approach, the deep semantic structure of language is transformed into a superficial structure through grammatical rules; this transformation process reveals the mental nature of the grammatical system (Chomsky, 1965).

M. A. Halliday, putting forward a functional approach, interprets grammar as a means of creating meaning. He distinguishes three main metafunctions of language: ideational - expressing reality; interpersonal - defining relationships in communication; textual - ensuring the coherence and cohesiveness of the text. The language system is based on a "choice system", that is, the speaker chooses a construction that is appropriate for the meaning from the available grammatical options (Halliday, 1994).

L. Bachman, in the communicative competence model, sees grammatical competence as part of organizational competence and divides it into two components: grammatical competence - mastery of grammatical rules, word formation, syntactic connections; text composition competence - control of the coherence, connection system and structure of the text (Bachman, 1990). These components, together with pragmatic and sociolinguistic factors, ensure the correct use of language in communication. In our opinion, the approaches of M. A. Halliday and L. Bachman are of paramount importance in interpreting grammar in integration with meaning, communication and text structure. Because in the views of F.

de Saussure, L.Bloomfield and N.Chomsky, grammar is mainly interpreted as a systemic or mental mechanism, and its communicative direction is limited.

All these theoretical models determine the content, structure and mechanisms of grammatical competence. In the process of improving this competence in philology students, it is important that the educational material is in a natural, contextual and meaningful form. Poetic texts are of particular importance as an effective linguodidactical tool in teaching grammatical competence, since they demonstrate the rhythmic, syntactic and semantic possibilities of grammatical units (Anders, 2013; Bredella, 2002).

L.Bloomfield, in his work “Language”, sees “grammar” as a unified complex of phonology (phonetic units) and morphology (morphemes and their combinations). L.Bloomfield notes that “language is an “empirical” aspect: “Language is a set of data that can only be confirmed by intuition,” and he also considered the issue of grammar in this context (Bloomfield, 1933). This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of integrating poetic texts into grammar instruction in higher education.

Methods. Grammatical competence is the ability to correctly and appropriately apply language rules and structures in an appropriate context (Bachman, 1990; Hymes, 1972). International research considers grammatical competence as an integral part of language acquisition at three levels: lexical-communicative, pragmatic and grammatical levels, which are inextricably linked (CEFR, 2001). As a result of teaching students grammar rules only through theoretical explanations, they encounter difficulties in applying them in the process of practical communication, which constitutes the main content of the pedagogical problem

Through the works of classical authors such as F.Schiller, H.Heine, J.V.Goethe, B.Brecht, such basic grammatical topics as tenses, adjective and noun declension, word order, passive forms, modality, inversion are studied in a practical way. Thus, the use of poetic materials allows strengthening grammatical competence, developing language sensitivity, and applying theoretical knowledge in the context of natural speech (Collie & Slater, 1987; Belke, 2009).

In the process of teaching grammar based on poetic texts, the linguistic and cognitive activity of students increases significantly. In this case, grammatical units are mastered not in isolation, but within a certain context, rhythm and semantic load (Ellis, 2006). As a result, students begin to understand not only the formal structure of grammatical forms, but also their communicative and pragmatic functions. In this regard, literary texts, in particular poetic samples, are an effective didactic tool for deepening grammatical knowledge and integrating them into the real speech process.

The SMILE method focuses on the study of grammatical units not only at the structural level but also in close connection with their meaning. It integrates content, imagery, and emotional aspects of language, allowing students to perceive grammar as a meaningful and expressive tool.

This method serves to develop grammatical competence in integration with aesthetic perception, taking into account the obvious manifestation of the rhythmic, stylistic and expressive functions of grammatical forms in poetic texts. In the SMILE approach, grammatical units are interpreted not as a structural system, but as a means of creating meaning and enhancing emotional impact.

In the process of working with poetic texts, phenomena such as inversion, repetition, grammatical parallelism are analyzed not only as syntactic devices, but also as elements that serve to emphasize the content, form a rhythmic tone and enhance the artistic effect. For example, the repeated use of verb forms or a change in word order, while enhancing the emotional background of the poem, reveal the functional possibilities of grammatical forms. As a result, the SMILE method allows for the development of the linguopoetic (aesthetic-grammatical) component of grammatical competence and ensures a deep assimilation of grammatical knowledge in terms of content, aesthetics and communication (see Figure 1):

S	Structure/Struktur Read the poem and identify its grammatical structures. Determine the placement of verbs, inversion, compound sentences, and tense forms.
M	Meaning/Bedeutung Identify the main ideas or messages conveyed through the poem and determine how they are tied to the poet's purpose or intention.
I	Imagery/Bildlichkeit Analyze how grammatical parallelism, repetition, or verb forms in the poem create images (descriptions).
L	Language/Sprache Choose one poetic grammatical form from the poem and change it into a normative (ordinary) grammatical equivalent.
E	Emotion/Emotion Identify how imperative, modal, or verb placements create an emotional impact at the poem's climax. Determine how these elements influence the reader's feelings.

Figure 1. Application of the SMILE method

The advantages of the SMILE method are:

- provides a systematic understanding of grammatical units within the framework of the structure of a poetic text;
- helps to consciously perceive the content and semantic function (meaning) of grammatical forms;
- through poetic imagery, it makes it possible to distinguish between the normative and aesthetic use of grammatical units;
- enhances the contextual selection and functional use of language;
- provides a deep understanding of the expressive and pragmatic effects of grammatical forms through the emotional component (emotion);
- serves to improve grammatical competence in an integrative, sustainable, and communicatively effective way in a poetic context.

Thus, SMILE methods serve as an effective methodological tool for improving grammatical competence on the basis of poetic texts. This method allows the mastery of grammatical units in integration with content and speech activity, developing grammatical sensitivity and conscious application skills in students. This approach creates a methodological basis for improving grammatical

competence in later stages by combining it with complex speech tasks and other language skills.

Based on the scientific and theoretical recommendations developed as a result of the research, the following methods were used to use the methodology for improving students' grammatical competence based on poetic texts in higher educational institutions and to determine the level of its effectiveness:

- forms of experimental work:

- diagnostic test – to determine the initial level of students' grammatical knowledge of the German language;

- experimental impact – improving students' grammatical competence based on poetic texts;

The control test is a final assessment of students' grammatical level in German.

In this study, the activities of the experimental and control groups were organized in a methodologically clearly differentiated manner. While the experimental group was focused on improving grammatical competence based on poetic texts, grammar teaching in the control group was conducted based on traditional methods. In particular, in the control group, grammatical topics were mastered through formal explanations, sample exercises in the textbook, translation and test tasks, and poetic texts were not used as a didactic tool. This approach allowed for a methodologically sound comparison of the results obtained in the experimental and control groups.

Participants of the experiment:

Experimental group (EG): students whose grammatical competence was trained on the basis of poetic texts;

Control group (CG): students taught using traditional methods.

The following methods were used in the experimental testing of our research work:

1. Comparison method – Evaluating the effectiveness of the methodology based on comparing the results of the experimental and control groups.
2. Diagnostic and monitoring method – assessing student knowledge as a result of tests, interviews, questionnaires, and control work.

3. Mathematical-statistical analysis method – analysis of the results of an experiment conducted in an experimental and control group using mathematical methods.

Types of lessons organized based on poetic text during the experimental process:

Table 1. shows a systematic classification of the types of lessons organized on the basis of poetic texts during the experimental process, the grammatical components and methodological approaches used in them. This structure provides the teacher with a clear methodological direction in integrating the poetic genre, its linguistic units and grammatical possibilities into the educational process. The table highlights the differentiation of lessons by grammatical focus and the need to choose appropriate methods for each type of text (see Table 1):

Table 1. Types of lessons based on poetic text, grammatical components and methodological approaches

No.	Text type	Grammatical component	Implementation method
1.	Lyric poem	Use of time	Verb analysis, tense change exercises
2.	Ballad	Syntax	Sentence structure analysis
3.	Epic poem	Cases	Analysis of prepositions, case forms

Table 1. shows that each of the poetic genres has specific methodological potential for improving grammatical competence. Lyric poems are effective in expressing verb tenses and their stylistic function, while ballads are convenient in teaching syntactic structures. Epic texts, on the other hand, have wide opportunities for identifying cases, prepositions and their semantic load. As a result, the harmonious introduction of linguistic features of poetic genres into the teaching process deepens students' theoretical knowledge and serves to consciously apply grammatical analysis in context.

During the pedagogical experiment, the effectiveness of the methodology for improving grammatical competence through poetic texts was assessed based on the following criteria. The criterion-based assessment system allows you

to objectively determine the extent to which students have formed such components as knowledge, skills, competence and creativity. Also, the variety of control forms serves to fully assess the practical manifestation of each competency (see Table 3):

Table 3. Criteria for evaluating effectiveness

No.	Component	Criteria	Control form
1.	Knowledge	Theoretical knowledge	Test
2.	Skill	Be able to use grammatical units correctly	Written assignment
3.	Qualification	Using grammatical units in oral speech	Conversation, dialogue
4.	Creativity	Expressing independent opinions based on poetry	Essay, creative work

The table shows that the assessment criteria cover all components of grammatical competence and serve to consistently determine the student's mastery of theoretical concepts, their application in practical situations, and their ability to think creatively.

While theoretical knowledge is assessed through tests, skills and competence are manifested in the activity in the speech process. The creativity criterion shows the level of the student's free, meaningful, and aesthetically justified use of grammatical units based on a poetic text. Thus, a systematic and integrative assessment approach provides a broad opportunity to determine the true effectiveness of the methodology.

As a result of using the methodology for improving students' grammatical competence based on poetic texts, the following competencies were assessed when assessing the level of students' knowledge of the German language:

1. Assessment of grammatical competence: tests; written analysis based on a poetic text; sentence construction and analysis exercises.
2. Assessment of lexical competence: finding synonyms and antonyms; using words based on context; translation tasks.
3. Assessment of speech competence: dialogue, spoken word recording; compose a story based

on the picture; grammatical correctness and consistency of speech.

4. Cultural competency assessment: expressing opinions that are appropriate to the cultural context; conversation about German culture and traditions.

The experimental study was conducted using mathematical and statistical analysis. To ensure the validity of the results obtained from the pedagogical experiment, the data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods. The chi-square (χ^2) test was applied to perform the statistical analysis.

Mathematical and statistical analysis of experimental and test work was performed based on the following criteria:

- The relative and average coefficients of variation of the average mastery indicators of the experimental and control groups were compared using the arithmetic mean method;
- The variation indicators of variability in the experimental groups were calculated and conclusions were drawn based on this;
- The sampling distribution polygons of the experimental and control groups were drawn, and the hypothesis of the equality of the mean values of the main sets was tested and concluded based on the distribution criterion of the chi-square (χ^2) method.

Conclusions were drawn from the results of mathematical and statistical calculations conducted during the pedagogical experiment.

Results. The study was conducted at Uzbekistan State World Languages University (UzSWLU), Bukhara State University (BSU) and Karakalpak State University (KSU). The variation indicators are presented for the experimental group ($n = 88$) and the control group ($n = 91$).

Table 4 presents a comparison of changes in the level of grammatical competence between the experimental group (EG) and control (CG) group, based on data from Uzbekistan State World Languages University. The table shows the results observed at the beginning and at the end of the experimental process, quantitatively reflecting the

effectiveness of the teaching methodology based on poetic texts (see Table 4).

Table 4. The level of development of students' grammatical competence at Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Grammatical Competence Level	Experimental Groups		Control Groups	
	Pre-test (55 students)	Post-test (55 students)	Pre-test (57 students)	Post-test (57 students)
Excellent	14	24	15	13
Average	25	24	26	23
Weak	16	7	16	21

The results of the table show that in the experimental group, a significant increase in grammatical competence was observed: the number of students with an “excellent” level more than doubled, while the number of students with a “low” level decreased sharply. In the control group, this change was much slower, and the indicators remained almost stable. This scientifically confirms that grammar lessons based on poetic texts improve the student’s theoretical and practical competence faster, deeper and more effectively.

Figure 2. Grammatical Competence Levels.

In the process of pedagogical experiment, mathematical and statistical calculations were carried out to assess the effectiveness of the proposed teaching

methodology. First, the results of Uzbekistan State World Languages University are presented, where the learning outcomes of the experimental and control groups are shown in detail. Statistical data shed light on the changes observed during the study and clearly demonstrated the impact of the methodology within this university.

The analysis then expanded to include the results from Bukhara State University and Karakalpak State University. This comparative approach allows for the identification of trends and differences across all three universities, providing a broader understanding of the results. The combined results serve to identify common patterns and provide a basis for drawing pedagogical conclusions.

The results show that the experimental and control groups were almost identical at the initial level, with the highest percentage of students at the “average” level. This means that although the students had sufficient grammatical competence at the beginning of the experiment, there were certain gaps in in-depth analysis and contextual application (see Table 5):

Table 5. Analysis of students’ grammatical competence by level of development (at the beginning of the experiment)

Educational institutions	Experiment group				Control group			
	Number of test takers	Excellent	Average	Low	Number of test takers	Excellent	Average	Low
UzSWLU	55	14	25	16	57	15	26	16
BSU	18	4	8	6	19	4	8	7
KSU	15	4	7	4	15	4	8	3
Total	88	22	40	26	91	23	42	26

At the end of the experimental-testing process, significant positive changes in students’ grammatical competence were clearly demonstrated. The number of students with an “excellent” level in the experimental group increased from 22 to 38, that is, almost doubled, which practically confirms the effectiveness of the methodology (see Table 6):

Table 6. Analysis of students' grammatical competence by level of development (at the end of the experiment)

Educational institutions	Experiment group				Control group			
	Number of test takers	Excellent	Average	Low	Number of test takers	Excellent	Average	Low
UzSWLU	55	24	24	7	57	13	23	21
BSU	18	8	8	2	19	5	7	7
KSU	15	6	7	2	15	4	7	4
Total	88	38	39	11	91	22	37	32

Figure 3 presents a comparison of the experimental results of our research, including the results of the table above (see Figure 3):

Figure 3. Analysis of students' grammatical competence by level of development.

The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the experimental group demonstrated higher effectiveness compared to the control group, with an efficiency coefficient of 1.11. The average coefficient of variation of the experimental and control groups is as follows:

$$L = \overline{X}_t - \overline{X}_n = 4.31 - 3.89 = 0.42$$

The findings demonstrate that the results of mathematical and statistical calculations of the post-experimental indicators of the experimental and control groups confirm that the mastery efficiency indicators of the

experimental groups are higher than those of the control groups. Now we present an analysis of the levels of improvement of students' grammatical competence as a result of teaching based on poetic texts by region (see Table 7):

Table. 7. Students' grammatical competence as a result of teaching based on poetic texts (*Analysis of development levels by region*)

Educational institutions	Confidence intervals				Average value		Efficiency	Average coefficient of variation
	Experiment group		Control group		Experiment group	Control group		
UzSWLU	4.17	4.45	3.70	4.02	4.31	3.86	1.12	0.45
BSU	4.19	4.47	3.73	4.06	4.33	3.89	1.11	0.44
KSU	4.12	4.41	3.85	4.15	4.27	4.00	1.08	0.28
Total	4.16	4.44	3.76	4.08	4.31	3.89	1.11	0.39

Concluding from the above indicators, we can see that the results of improving students' grammatical competence as a result of teaching German based on poetic texts are more effective in the experimental group than in the control group (see Figure 4.)

Figure 4. Grammatical competence indicators of development levels.

Discussion. The results of the study indicate that the integration of poetic texts into grammar instruction has a

significant positive impact on students' grammatical competence. The observed improvement in the experimental groups can be explained by the contextual, expressive, and emotionally engaging nature of poetic texts, which facilitate deeper understanding of grammatical structures (Collie & Slater, 1987; Belke, 2009).

Furthermore, the use of poetic texts allows students to perceive grammar not only as a system of rules but also as a meaningful and functional component of language use (Halliday, 1994; Bachman, 1990). This contributes to the development of both linguistic accuracy and communicative competence. The findings are consistent with previous research emphasizing the importance of contextualized and integrative approaches in language teaching (Ellis, 2006; Fotos & Ellis, 2001). The outcomes of the mathematical and statistical analyzes reveal that using poetic texts to develop grammatical competence is highly effective. The experimental groups exhibited an 11% greater improvement compared to the control groups, illustrating the method's potential to strengthen students' language abilities in an engaging and meaningful manner. These findings provide a reliable basis for considering the broader application of this approach across educational institutions in Uzbekistan.

In light of these results, it is advisable for educators to integrate carefully chosen poetic texts into language curricula to enhance grammatical competence. Furthermore, curriculum developers and policymakers may explore adapting and expanding this methodology for wider implementation, thereby encouraging innovative and culturally rich teaching strategies. Future research could investigate the long-term effects of literary integration in grammar instruction and assess its relevance across diverse student populations.

Conclusion. The findings of this study confirm that integrating poetic texts into grammar instruction is an effective and innovative approach to developing students' grammatical competence in higher education. The results of the pedagogical experiment demonstrate that students in the experimental groups achieved significantly higher levels of grammatical competence compared to those in the control groups, with an overall improvement of 11%.

The effectiveness of this methodology can be explained by the contextual, expressive, and emotionally engaging nature of poetic texts, which allow students to understand grammatical structures in a meaningful and communicative context. This approach not only enhances linguistic accuracy but also supports the development of students' interpretative and creative abilities.

From a pedagogical perspective, the study highlights the importance of integrating literary materials into grammar instruction as a means of promoting deeper learning and increasing student motivation. Therefore, it is recommended that educators incorporate carefully selected poetic texts into language curricula to support the development of grammatical competence in higher education.

Future research may focus on examining the long-term impact of this methodology, as well as its applicability across different languages, educational contexts, and learner groups. Such studies would contribute to further refinement and wider implementation of integrative approaches in language education.

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